

Suicidal Thought and Expression through Art: A Case Report

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Abstract:- Suicide is a serious psychological problem that is made worse by psychiatric diseases, personal loss, and other stressful life events. Suicidal thoughts and ideas were conveyed in a variety of ways by clients who attempted suicide, but noncommunicable ones should be closely monitored without misunderstanding or misinterpretation to prevent precious human loss.

This case study was centered on a 17-year-old married girl who had suicidal thoughts and a history of three suicide attempts. Suicidal ideation and thoughts were evaluated by observation and semi-structured interview methods with open-ended questionnaires that included personal, professional, familial, and socioeconomic variables. Surprisingly, the client drew pictures using pencils to describe her suicidal thoughts and the triggers that led to them.

It is quite simple for the medical professional to comprehend the etiological variables that significantly contribute to the patient's thoughts of suicide and ideas. Additionally, art will play a crucial part as a motivator to subconsciously communicate their demands and expectations from the family and society, which can inhibit the severity of symptoms by deflecting the mind and meeting their needs. Additionally, it inadvertently encourages the medical professional, the patient's family, and other people to learn about persistent suicidal thoughts and ideas of clients, suicide warning signals, and methods for controlling and preventing suicidal thoughts.

Keywords:- Suicidal thoughts and Ideas, Art, Painting, Drawing, Reducing Symptoms.

I. INTRODUCTION

The most prevalent psychiatric problem is suicidality, and recent years have seen a significant increase in instances as a result of the stress and expectations of modern life. Nearly 20 times as many individuals attempt suicide each year as those who really succeed (WHO, 2019). Nearly 800,000 people worldwide die by suicide each year. In addition, if the client does not disclose suicidal ideation and thoughts in a suitable manner at the appropriate time, it leads to the client's death. This makes it extremely difficult for medical experts and family members to identify such thoughts and ideation. Furthermore, it is not consistent and varies depending on risk exposure and stimulants such

as social discord, job loss, loved one loss, post-traumatic events, and other associative diseases.

II. CASE REPORT

A. Method:

This case study focused on a 17-year-old girl who had suicidal thoughts and a history of three suicide attempts admitted in female psychiatric ward was assessed by observation and semi-structured interview methods with open-ended questionnaires that included personal, professional, familial, and socioeconomic variables. Surprisingly, the client chose not to communicate verbally and instead used a pencil diagram (a diagrammatic art) to explain her suicidal thoughts and the stimuli that prompted them.

B. Discussion:

Numerous clinical investigative techniques, such as the Thematic Apperception Test, BSR5-5, C-SSRS, GSIS, ISST, and SBQ-R, which all aim to understand psychology and its limitations, were used in practice to evaluate clients' suicidal thoughts and ideas. However, using client information to therapeutic decisions in the treatment plan makes sense.

With the use of art, which is regarded as a widespread form of emotional expression, one can effectively share their ideas and imaginary worlds with others. It is relevant when a client is expressing their emotions and has suicidal thoughts or ideas. Although there are many other visual presentations in art, such as painting, drawing, sculpture, and theatre dance. However, the client with psychological impairment uses drawing and painting the most frequently to communicate their emotions.

One can observe that in a client with suicidal ideation, the point-to-control and prevention of suicidal thoughts and ideation plays a crucial role in determining the cause behind the suicide thought, ultimately directing healthcare professionals to understand the client's current psychological health condition and to plan an appropriate treatment modality. Additionally, the expression of a client's suicidal feelings and thoughts by Art is regarded as a therapeutic technique that subtly encourages the client to express their emotional pain and minimizes emotional distress, which in turn reduces suicidal thoughts.

In addition, it makes a primary care provider aware of the client's activity, enables them to give the client the

necessary attention at the right time, and can ensure quality medical care.

III. ILLUSTRATION/ DIAGRAMS BY CLIENT

Fig – 1: Picture illustration of symptoms of client expressed her preoccupation Suicidal thoughts and ideas

Fig – 2: Picture illustration of symptoms of suicidal thoughts and ideas

IV. CONCLUSION

As a result of this study, it is clear that using art as a tool for clients who have a history of suicidal thoughts and ideas is possible. It can serve as a tool for delivering high-quality treatment, a technique for ensuring resilience, and a preventative step against suicide.

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